

ToC Figure

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3 **Photophysical Characterization and Biointeractions of NIR-Squaraine Dyes for**
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6 ***In-vitro* and *In-Vivo* Bioimaging**
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Abstract

The increasing demand for reliable near-infrared (NIR) probes exhibiting enduring fluorescence in living systems and facile compatibility with biomolecules such as antibodies and proteins is driven by the expanding use of NIR imaging in clinical diagnostics. To address this demand, a series of carboxy-functionalized unsymmetrical squaraine dyes (SQ-27, SQ-212, & SQ-215) along with non-carboxy functionalized SQ-218 absorbing and emitting in the NIR wavelength range were designed and synthesized followed by photophysical characterization. This study focused on the impact of structural variations in alkyl chain length, carboxy functionality positioning, and spacer chain length on dye aggregation and interaction with Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) as a model protein. In phosphate buffer (PB), the absorption intensity of the dyes markedly decreased, accompanied by pronounced shoulders indicative of dye aggregation and complete fluorescence quenching was seen in contrast to organic solvents. However, in the presence of BSA in PB, there was a remarkable enhancement in absorption intensity, while regaining the fluorescence coupled with the increase in intensity with increasing BSA concentrations, signifying the impact of dye-BSA interactions on preventing aggregation. Further analysis of Job's plot unveiled a 2:1 interaction ratio between BSA and all dyes, while the binding studies revealed a robust binding affinity (K_a) in the order of 10^7 /mol. SQ-212 and SQ-215 were further tested for their *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* imaging capabilities. Notably, SQ-212 demonstrated non-permeability to cells, while SQ-215 exhibited easy penetration and prominent cytoplasmic localization in *in-vitro* studies. Injection of the dyes into laboratory mice showcased their efficacy in visualization, displaying stable and intense fluorescence in tissues for 120 minutes without toxicity, organ damage, or behavioral changes. Thus, SQ-212 and SQ-215 are promising

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3 candidates for imaging applications, holding potential for non-invasive cellular and diagnostic
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5 imaging, as well as biomarker detection when coupled with specific vectors in living systems.
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8 **Keywords:** Squaraine dyes; BSA interaction; Dye aggregation; Non-covalent labeling; *in-vitro* &
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10 *in-vivo* Bioimaging.

11 12 **1. Introduction**

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15 The use of bioimaging techniques allows for non-invasive and real-time visualization of biological
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17 processes within tissues and internal organs, offering qualitative and quantitative insights at the
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19 cellular or molecular level. In comparison to traditional imaging methods like Magnetic Resonance
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21 Imaging (MRI), ultrasound imaging, X-ray, Computed Tomography (CT scan), and radionuclide
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23 imaging, optical imaging has emerged as a highly advantageous technique in medical research.
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25 This is due to its exceptional attributes, including high spatial resolution, portability, real-time
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27 display, heightened sensitivity, cost-effectiveness, and non-invasive nature ^{1,2}. Fluorescent probes
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29 offer valuable insights into the role of biomolecules and can be designed to target and study
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31 specific organelles in both healthy and diseased conditions. Fluorescence-based imaging has been
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33 employed in the past ^{3,4}. Fluorescence emission in the near infra-red (NIR) region, bears profound
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35 significance as significant interest in this arena has increased, pertaining to sensing, non-covalent
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37 binding, and imaging ⁵⁻⁷. Over the past decade, the development of highly effective fluorescence
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39 imaging probes, including organic dyes, quantum dots (QDs), fluorescent proteins/peptide-
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41 conjugates, nanomaterials, and carbon dots, has garnered significant interest. However, certain
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43 limitations such as high photobleaching rates, poor signal-to-noise ratio, short luminescence
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45 lifetimes, and limited biocompatibility hinder the progress in developing fluorescent probes. This
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47 can be overcome by utilizing wavelength-tunable dyes that can absorb and emit light in the near-
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49 infrared (NIR) region of the electromagnetic spectrum. The emission in the visible range is plagued
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3 naturally by the autofluorescence of inherent biomolecules and certain proteins, leading to large
4 background noise, severe light scattering, reduced signal-to-noise ratio, and shallow penetration
5 depth, resulting in low imaging quality. Hence compounds absorbing and emitting in the NIR
6 region offer higher sensitivity, deeper tissue penetration, low light scattering, and less signal-to-
7 noise ratio due to the absence of biomolecules' natural autofluorescence ⁸⁻¹⁰. These advantages
8 have propelled the exploration and development of NIR probes for a wide range of biomedical and
9 scientific purposes. Harnessing the potential of NIR fluorescence for improved sensitivity,
10 specificity, and selectivity in areas such as biological sensing, molecular imaging, drug delivery,
11 and biomarker detection has grown manifold. Great attention has been drawn to applying NIR
12 probes in several areas of biosensing and bioimaging, including tissue perfusion, vascular
13 mapping, inflammation monitoring, tumor diagnosis and imaging ^{11,12}, and for various clinical and
14 preclinical diagnosis and monitoring ¹³⁻¹⁶.

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17 Squaraine class of dyes, are characterized by their unique aromatic four-membered ring
18 core (3,4-dihydroxycyclobut-3-ene-1,2-dione) derived from squaric acid, linked by aromatic
19 heterocyclic moieties at either ends leading to donor-acceptor-donor molecular arrangement. Their
20 application as fluorescent labels or probes for sensing and imaging research is of significant
21 interest because their wavelength tunable capabilities make them absorb and emit from visible to
22 NIR wavelength regions ^{17,18}. Squaraine dyes also possess high molar absorptivity and reasonably
23 good quantum yields, ¹⁹ and good photostability ²⁰⁻²². By rational molecular design, Squaraine
24 dye's absorption and emission wavelengths can be tuned from visible to IR wavelength, making
25 them suitable for sensing and imaging ²³. Thus Squaraine dyes, with their unique chemical and
26 physical properties, find themselves as NIR fluorescent probes in a plethora of applications such
27 as environmental sensing ²⁴, molecular sensing ^{25,26}, bioimaging ²⁷⁻²⁹, and biochemical labeling

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3^{30,31}. However, their application under physiological conditions is limited by factors such as
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intrinsic chemical instability and self-aggregation. The fluorescence intensities of squaraine dyes are significantly compromised due to aggregation leading to even complete quenching. Therefore dye interactions with serum proteins such as BSA and HSA under physiological conditions have been studied to overcome this problem^{32–34}.

This work reports the synthesis, characterization, and photophysical studies of four new unsymmetrical squaraine dyes (**SQ-27**, **SQ-212**, **SQ-215**, and **SQ-218**), as shown in **Fig. 1**. Except **SQ-218**, the other squaraine dyes under investigation contain a -COOH group to facilitate coupling with biocompatible molecules such as peptides, oligonucleotides, or proteins, as well as to highlight the importance of the -COOH group for non-covalent protein labeling and site-selective binding with carrier proteins such as BSA or HSA. Symmetrical dyes containing multiple -COOH groups introduces complexity in the conjugation process with specific peptides, leading to side reactions and a subsequent decrease in yield. This complication also contributes to intricate synthetic procedures. On the other hand, unsymmetrical dyes with a single -COOH group can streamline the synthesis of dye conjugates, facilitating a more simple and straightforward process. All the dyes are based on benzo[e]indole moieties on either side of the squaric acid core. **SQ-212** contains a long *N*-substituted dodecyl alkyl group on one-half of the dye, whereas **SQ-215** contains a short *N*-substituted ethyl group. The other half anchors the *N*-substituted -COOH group for the dyes **SQ-212** and **SQ-215**. **SQ-27** bears the direct functionalization of the -COOH group on the benzo[e]indole ring. This study then explores the interaction of these dyes with BSA as a model protein in phosphate buffer to investigate the dye's suitability for biosensing and bioimaging applications. The influence and effect of varying alkyl chain length and position of the -COOH group on the interactions with Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) as a model protein was then followed

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3 by *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies involving SQ-212 and SQ-215, with both showing promising
4 capabilities as bioimaging probes. A stable and reproducible signal was obtained from injecting
5 the compounds in white fur-bearing laboratory mice, with clear tracking of the dyes until the
6 removal from the organism was possible. Thus, indicating efficiency and applicability of dyes and
7 their possible conjugates for *in-vivo* imaging techniques.
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34 **Figure 1.** Molecular structure of the carboxy-functionalized unsymmetrical squaraine dyes
35 under investigation with varying alkyl chain lengths, spacer lengths, and position of the carboxy
36 group.
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43 2. Experimental

44 2.1. Materials and Methods

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46 All the chemicals used for synthesis were procured from TCI chemicals and Sigma Aldrich. The
47 dyes and the dye intermediates were analyzed by FAB-Mass spectroscopy in positive ion
48 monitoring mode followed by high-resolution mass spectroscopy (HRMS). Nuclear Magnetic
49 Resonance (NMR) spectra for structural elucidations were recorded on a JEOL JNM A500 MHz
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3 spectrometer in CDCl_3 solvent with TMS as the internal reference. Solution state electronic
4 absorption studies were carried out using a JASCO V-530 UV/VIS/IR spectrophotometer, while
5 the fluorescence emission spectra were recorded using a JASCO FP-6600 spectrophotometer. For
6 emission studies, the excitation wavelength was 610 nm for all experiments. The excitation (B)
7 and emission (W) bandwidths were kept at 5 and 2 for all studies.

17 2.2. Fluorescence Quantum Yield

18 The fluorescence quantum yield (ϕ) of the dyes was calculated by the comparative method³⁵ with
19 Rhodamine 6G as the standard, using the following equation.

$$24 \quad Q = Q_R \left[\frac{Grad}{Grad_R} \right] \left[\frac{\eta^2}{\eta_R^2} \right] \quad (1)$$

25 Q_R represents the quantum yield of the reference or known sample. $Grad$ signifies the gradient
26 derived from the plot illustrating the integrated fluorescence intensity against the corresponding
27 absorbance, while η stands for the refractive index of the solvent, $Grad_R$ denotes the gradient
28 determined for the reference sample. Different concentrations of the dyes and Rhodamine 6G were
29 prepared in CHCl_3 with the maximum absorption intensity not crossing 0.3. The values of Q_R for
30 rhodamine 6G (0.95)³⁶ and η for CHCl_3 (1.44)³⁷ were taken from the literature. The emission
31 spectra were obtained by utilizing the absorption spectra's respective absorption maximum (λ_{max})
32 as the excitation wavelength. Subsequently, the integrated fluorescence intensity, represented as
33 the area under the emission peak, was measured. A graph correlating integrated fluorescence
34 intensity with the corresponding absorbance was constructed to determine the gradient.

51 2.3. Preparation of stock solutions and study of dye-BSA interaction

52 1 mM stock solutions of the dyes were prepared in DMSO and CHCl_3 and diluted to the required
53 concentration when required. Since the dyes were not soluble in PB, the 1mM DMSO stock
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3 solution was diluted to the working concentration of 10 μM and 2 μM in PB. The dye solutions in
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5 PB were stable for more than a week. 100 μM stock solution of BSA was prepared in 0.1M
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7 phosphate buffer (pH = 7.4). For the dye-BSA interactions, the working volume of the final
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9 solution was 5 mL, in which the dye's concentration was kept constant at 2 μM while varying the
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11 BSA concentration from 100 nM to 50 μM . The dye-BSA solution was incubated at room
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13 temperature for 1 hour with continuous stirring before recording the respective absorption and
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15 emission spectra. The binding constants (K_a) were calculated from previously reported
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17 procedures³⁸ to study the extent of the Dye-BSA interaction.
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20 21 22 *2.4. Synthesis of squaraine dyes and dye intermediates*

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24 The squaraine dyes **SQ-212**, **SQ-215**, and **SQ-218** were synthesized according to **scheme 1**, and
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26 **SQ-27** was synthesized in combination with **scheme 1** and **scheme 2**. For detailed synthetic
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28 procedures and spectral data, see supplementary information.
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Scheme 1. Synthesis of unsymmetrical squaraine dyes **SQ-212**, **SQ-215** and **SQ-218**.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of unsymmetrical squaraine dye **SQ-27**. (A) Benzophenone hydrazone, Pd(OAc)₂, S-BINAP, toluene, RT, N₂ atmosphere. (B) Sodium *tert*-butoxide, 80°C. (C) Methylisopropyl ketone, PTSA, EtOH, reflux, 18 hrs. (D) Iodoethane, acetonitrile, reflux 24hrs. (E) Toluene:butanol 1:1, reflux, 18-24 hrs. (F) 10% NaOH, ethanol, reflux, 30min.

2.5. Fluorescence of squaraine dyes upon interaction with biological molecules

Fluorescent dyes were diluted to a final concentration of 10 μM in either H₂O or phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) with 1% DMSO. 200 μl solution containing the biologically active substance were prepared in 96-well black plates containing 1 % Bovine serum albumin (BSA), 10⁷ cells/well of Nemeth-Kellner lymphoma cells (NK/Ly), and ascites fluid in separate wells. NK/Ly cells were grown as a liquid tumor in ascites fluid. Ascites were isolated from the peritoneal cavity of mice with a syringe. This cellular suspension was then centrifuged at 1500g to separate cells and acellular supernatant – referred as ascites fluid³⁹. After sedimentation, the cells were washed twice in PBS and used for analysis, while the ascites fluid was dissolved to 50% v/v in PBS due to the technical need for equalizing the volume in all samples. Additionally, some wells were supplemented with a protease inhibitor cocktail at a final concentration of 0.5% (Sigma Aldrich P8340), This mixture consists of distinct components, namely AEBSF at a concentration of 104 mM, Aprotinin at 80 μM, Bestatin at 4 mM, E-64 at 1.4 mM, Leupeptin at 2 mM, and Pepstatin A

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3 at 1.5 mM. Then squaraine dyes were added to each well to reach a final concentration of 10 μ M
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5 and their fluorescence was studied using Perkin Elmer BioAssay reader HST7000 at excitation of
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7 680/10 nm and emission 720/20 nm and excitation of 780/10 nm and emission 820/20 nm.
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10 11 12 *2.6. Fluorescent microscopy*

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14 Fluorescent microscopy was performed as described ⁴⁰ with an Olympus BX51 fluorescent
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16 microscope (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan) equipped with Omega Filters XF407 filter set with
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18 excitation at 630/30 nm and emission 710/80 nm (Omega Filters, Brattleboro, USA) and cooled
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20 Sony IMX585 sensor-based camera. for NIR imaging. Both 40x 0.75NA, 90x 1.0NA water
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22 immersion and 100x 1.4NA oil immersion objectives were used for live cell imaging. Native
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24 Olympus software was used for image processing. Alternatively, the Keyence BZ-X800
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26 fluorescent microscope was used with an appropriate Cy5 fluorescent filter. For image analysis
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28 and quantifications, the ImageJ software, developed by the National Institutes of Health in
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30 Bethesda, MD, USA, was employed. All image analysis tasks were executed using consistent
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32 parameters, which included fixed settings for exposure and compensation.
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40 *2.7. Study of cell permeability of squaraine dyes*

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42 NK/Ly cells grown in ascites fluid were centrifuged at 1000g to separate the ascites fluid, followed
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44 by suspending the cells in Hanks' Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS). Squaraine dyes were added to
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46 this solution to a final concentration of 50 nM and incubated at 37°C during the indicated time,
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48 then put on a slide, covered with a coverslip and imaged. Imaging of squaraine dyes was done
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50 using fluorescent channels suitable for Cy5.
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53 *2.8. Application of squaraine dyes for in vivo imaging.*

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3 White laboratory mice of Balb/c line being 12-week-old and weighting 20-25 g were used.
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5 **Animals were anaesthetized and injected intraperitoneal (IP) with 10 μ M of squaraine dye in H₂O**
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7 **(containing 1% DMSO) per mouse.** Animals were immediately imaged using LiCor Pearl Trilogy
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9 fluorescence analyzer using ex. with 685 nm laser and emission at 700 nm channel. The animal
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11 studies were approved by the local ethical committee of Danylo Halytsky Lviv National Medical
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13 University (Permission 20201221/P9) and conducted according to the guidelines of the Federation
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15 of European Laboratory Animal Science Associations (FELASA).
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22 **3. Results and Discussions**

23 *3.1. Photophysical characterization*

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25 After their successful synthesis, purification, and characterization, the new squaraine dyes were
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27 subjected to photophysical investigation using electronic absorption and emission spectroscopies
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29 in chloroform, DMSO solvents, and phosphate buffer (pH = 7.4). The optical characterization
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31 results are summarized in **Table 1** (in CHCl₃) and **Table 2** (in DMSO & Phosphate buffer). **Fig.2**
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33 shows the absorption and emission spectra of the dyes in chloroform solvent. From **Table 1**, it is
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35 evident that the varying alkyl chain length and position of -COOH has minimal effect on the λ_{max} .
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37 All the dyes show sharp and intense light absorption between 666 nm - 672 nm wavelength region.
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39 The dyes also show a very high molar extinction coefficient, ranging from $1.7 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$
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41 to $2.52 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, with the highest being for **SQ-215**. The excitation wavelength was
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43 slightly below the corresponding λ_{max} of the absorption spectrum at 610 nm. The dyes exhibited
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45 an emission peak between 680 nm - 690 nm wavelength region, with a small Stokes shift of 16-20
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47 nm. This sharp and intense light absorption of squaraine dyes is associated with the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$
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electronic transitions. A small value of the observed Stokes shift depicts the rigidity of the molecules and lack of conformational changes after the photoexcitation.

Figure 2. Electronic absorption (solid line) and fluorescence emission (dashed line) spectra of the squaraine dyes in $CHCl_3$ ($10 \mu M$).

Table 1. Optical parameters for squaraine dyes in $10 \mu M$ $CHCl_3$ solution.

Dye	$\lambda_{max}(Abs)$ (nm)	$\lambda_{max}(Emi)$ (nm)	Stokes shift (nm)	Molar extinction coefficient (ϵ) $\times 10^5$ dm^3 $mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$	Quantum Yield (ϕ)
SQ-27	672	688	16	2.28	0.12
SQ-212	668	684	16	1.72	0.14
SQ-215	666	686	20	2.52	0.16
SQ-218	666	682	16	2.21	0.16

One of the most critical parameters in developing fluorescent probes is the fluorescence quantum yield (ϕ), defined as the ratio of absorbed photons to emitted photons⁴¹. The product of the ϕ and ϵ determines the brightness of the fluorophore, in other words, the strength of the fluorescence

signal. As indicated by **Table 1**, in chloroform, these dyes exhibit ϕ in the range of 0.12 – 0.16, typical of squaraine dyes.

Table 2. *Optical parameters of squaraine dyes in DMSO (10 μ M) and PB (10 μ M), respectively.*

Dyes	DMSO				Phosphate Buffer $\lambda_{\max}(\text{Abs})$ (nm)	
	$\lambda_{\max}(\text{Abs})$ (nm)	$\lambda_{\max}(\text{Emi})$ (nm)	Stokes's shift (nm)	Molar extinction coefficient (ϵ) $\times 10^5 \text{ dm}^{-3}$ $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	Main Peak	Shoulder Peak(s)
SQ-27	680	696	16	2.47	674	626
SQ-212	676	692	16	1.71	674	622
SQ-215	674	694	20	2.44	650	588,686
SQ-218	674	692	18	2.24	676	632, 720

Optical parameters deduced from electronic absorption and fluorescence emission spectral investigations for the dyes in DMSO and phosphate buffer are summarized in **Table 2**. In DMSO, all the dyes show sharp and intense light absorption between 674 nm - 680 nm wavelength region, with a very high molar extinction coefficient. The dyes exhibited similar behavior with an emission peak between 692 nm - 696 nm wavelength region, with a small Stokes shift of 16-20 nm. Compared to chloroform, the dyes in DMSO exhibited a red shift of about 8-10 nm in the absorption and emission spectra. To investigate the interactions between dyes and biomolecules for biosensing applications, Phosphate buffer solution (PB), pH = 7.4, is most commonly used as it mimics the physiological conditions. Hence, the electronic absorption spectra were measured in 0.1 M PB solution (pH 7.4), as shown in **Fig.3**. Apart from the primary $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition, Squaraine dyes also exhibit a vibronic shoulder in chloroform becomes more prominent, developing into a prominent peak, which has been reported to be an indicator of molecular aggregation. Aggregation in Squaraine and cyanine dyes is well-known due to their flat molecular structures^{42,43}. A higher absorbance ratio for the vibronic shoulder against the main monomeric dye peak indicates enhanced dye aggregation⁴⁴.

Figure 3. Electronic absorption spectra of Squaraine dyes ($10 \mu\text{M}$) in 0.1 M PB .

A perusal of **Fig.3** reveals that the vibronic shoulder bands in PB get highly pronounced compared to that observed in CHCl_3 or DMSO solutions, indicative of the formation of dye-aggregates in PB. Squaraine dyes can form aggregates through non-covalent interactions, such as $\pi - \pi$ stacking, hydrophobic or hydrophilic interactions, van der Waals forces, electrostatic forces, and hydrogen bonding^{45,46}. Generally, two types of aggregates, bathochromically shifted J-aggregates and hypsochromically shifted H-aggregates, are reported in Squaraine dyes⁴⁷. H-aggregates are primarily characterized by a blue-shifted peak and large Stokes shift compared to the monomer/main peak, while the J-aggregates are characterized by a narrow red-shifted peak with a small Stokes shift⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰. The increased dye aggregation in PB is greatly enhanced due to the conducive environment provided by the water to form hydrogen bonds between the dye and water molecules⁵¹. The presence of the $-\text{COOH}$ functional group on dyes **SQ-27**, **SQ-212**, and **SQ-215** further promotes dye aggregation, which can be confirmed from the spectra of **SQ-218**, which

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3 lacks a -COOH group, the main peak's intensity is relatively higher than the shoulder peak (**Fig.3**).
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5 Carboxylic acid group tends to act as both hydrogen bond acceptor and donor ⁵². Therefore, the
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7 presence of the -COOH group in the molecular framework can significantly increase the chances
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9 of hydrogen bond formation in aqueous media. The chain length also influences the dye aggregate
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11 formation in PB. In the case of *N*-ethyl substituted **SQ-215**, the formation of both H-aggregates
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13 and J-aggregates is seen (**Fig.3**). The peak of H-aggregates appears around 588 nm, whereas the
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15 peak of J-aggregates appears at around 686 nm. In the case of **SQ-27**, and **SQ-212**, only H-
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17 aggregates formation is seen, with the main peak above 670 nm and the shoulder peak around 620
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19 nm. This is due to the long alkyl chain substitution (octyl and dodecyl), which reduces the
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21 formation of aggregates due to steric hindrances. Long alkyl chains also increase the lipophilicity
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23 of the dye molecules, thereby slightly decreasing the extent of aggregate formation due to the
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25 hydrophobic effect ⁵³. **SQ-218** containing both ethyl and dodecyl chains shows the presence of
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27 both the aggregates. However, the shoulder and main peak are red-shifted compared to other dyes.
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29 The peak corresponding to H-aggregates and J-aggregates appears at 632 nm and 720 nm,
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31 respectively. The small hump observed at 676 nm corresponds to the main peak. Thus, long alkyl
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33 chains in the molecular framework prevent J-aggregates formation, promoting only the formation
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35 of H-aggregates, which can be exploited to control the aggregates' formation behavior selectively.
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37 Fluorescence emission spectra showed complete quenching of the fluorescence for all the dyes in
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39 PB. Thus, these dyes are ideal and promising probes for fluorescence on/off and FRET-based
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41 biosensing applications. This is advantageous because the probes can be tailored to enhance the
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43 fluorescence signal upon adding the analyte of interest, such as biomolecules of clinical
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45 significance. Thus, under physiological conditions they stay in *fluorescent-off* state and in
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3 *fluorescent-on* state upon the interaction of analyte. To further validate this, the interaction of these
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5 dyes with BSA as model protein was studied in PB.
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10 3.2. Interaction of dyes with BSA

11 Labeling biomolecules with fluorescent probes by non-covalent methods is preferred in biosensing
12 and bioimaging applications because it avoids the complications of a chemical reaction and
13 purification steps and provides quick response times ²⁸. In this regard, Human Serum Albumin
14 (HSA)/BSA has been used as a model protein to study the interaction of probes with proteins.
15 Patonay and co-workers first studied the non-covalent labeling of NIR dyes with HSA ⁵⁴. Due to
16 its high homology with HSA in the amino acid sequences, BSA has prominently been used as a
17 model protein to investigate the interactions between dye and protein ^{55,56}. It can be seen from
18 **Fig.4** that with the increasing concentrations of BSA, a decrease in the intensity of the **SQ-27's**
19 shoulder peak and an increase in the intensity of the main peak at 674 nm is observed, indicating
20 the prevention of dye aggregation due to dye-BSA interactions. At the same time, this enhanced
21 dye-BSA interaction led to the reappearance of fluorescence signal at 678 nm with a tremendous
22 increase with increasing concentrations of BSA.
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Figure 4. Absorption and emission spectral changes for the dye **SQ-27** ($2\ \mu\text{M}$) upon interacting with the varying concentrations of BSA.

Long alkyl chain (dodecyl), substituted dye **SQ-212** also followed a similar trend of decrease in dye aggregation with a concomitant increase in the fluorescence intensity with increasing concentration of BSA, which is shown in **Fig.5**, but with a differential enhancement in the fluorescence intensities upon their interaction with BSA. **SQ-212** demonstrated nearly two times enhanced fluorescence compared to the dye **SQ-27** counterpart. This could be associated with their different structural features leading to differential interaction with BSA. It can be seen from **Fig. 1** that **SQ-27** contains $-\text{COOH}$ directly substituted in the main aromatic ring, while **SQ-212** contains the $-\text{COOH}$ group substituted in the *N*-alkyl side chain with different spacer lengths, which will be discussed later by structure-property correlations. Investigation of the concentration-dependent differential changes in the fluorescence intensities for different sensitizers revealed that the dyes **SQ-212**, and **SQ-27** are sensitive to BSA up to $1\ \mu\text{M}$, and $5\ \mu\text{M}$, respectively.

Figure 5. Changes in the fluorescence spectra of dyes **SQ-212** as a function of varying concentrations of BSA.

To understand the role of alkyl chain length on the nature of aggregate formation and their impact on interaction with BSA, analogous dye probes of **SQ-212** with short alkyl chain length (ethyl) as **SQ-215** were designed and subjected to their optical characterization and interaction with BSA. **Fig.6** depicts the absorption and fluorescence spectral changes for dye **SQ-215** upon its interaction with different concentrations of BSA. A perusal of this figure corroborates that with increasing concentrations of BSA, there is an initial and slight blue shift up to 5 μM in the peak rising out of the formation of J-aggregates with little change in the absorption intensities of all three peaks appearing at 588 nm, 650 nm and, 686 nm. After the further increase in BSA concentration beyond 5 μM , the J-aggregate peak blue shifts and merges with the main peak, with the new peak appearing at 672 nm showing a sharper peak along with the increase in the intensity. On the other hand, the H-aggregate peak at 588 nm red-shifts and becomes insignificant similar to that of the monomer's absorption. Thus, at BSA concentrations from 5 μM onwards, the breaking of H-aggregates and J-

aggregates leads to the appearance of the fluorescence signal at 678 nm, whose intensity increases with BSA concentration. **SQ-215** was sensitive to BSA up to 1 μM .

Figure 6. Absorption and emission spectra of **SQ-215** (2 μM) with varying concentrations of BSA.

In contrast to the dyes bearing $-\text{COOH}$ functional group, the dye-BSA interaction of **SQ-218** lacking the $-\text{COOH}$ group was quite different, as shown in **Fig.7**. Interestingly, there was no change in the aggregation behavior of **SQ-218** in both absorption and emission studies, which is further affirmed by the lack of appearance of any fluorescence signal with increasing concentrations of BSA. This suggests the need and importance of a suitable functional group for non-covalent interactions between the dye molecule and protein. Throughout this study, there was no denaturation of the BSA caused by the dyes, as the peak at 280 nm (**Fig. 4, 6, & 7**) attributed to BSA that increases in intensity with the increasing concentrations of BSA confirms this. BSA contains two separate active sites: one being a hydrophobic site labeled as Site-I, and the other a hydrophilic site, referred to as site II. The binding interactions of site I are primarily hydrophobic

in nature, whereas the binding interactions of site II, involve a combination of hydrophobic, hydrogen bonding, and electrostatic interactions^{57–59}.

Figure 7. Absorption and emission spectra of **SQ-218** ($2 \mu\text{M}$) with varying concentrations of **BSA**.

Observing all the dye's interactions with BSA, it is evident that a $-\text{COOH}$ group in the dye's structure is essential for them to interact with BSA and break the formation of the aggregates. This is affirmed, as the dye **SQ-218** lacking the $-\text{COOH}$ group showed no fluorescence signal or change in the absorption spectra with increasing concentrations of BSA. This indicates that this class of Squaraine dyes (with two benzo[e]indole moieties) most probably interacts with site-II through hydrophilic interactions with hydrogen bonding as the most probable one. To further investigate this, the dye-BSA conjugate was subjected to ligand displacement studies with well-known site-specific ligands such as dansylamide (DNSA) for site I and dansylproline (DP) for site II^{60–62}.

The addition of varying concentrations of DP to **SQ-215-BSA** conjugate resulted in a gradual decrease in fluorescence intensity (**Fig.8**), which is due to the displacement of **SQ-215** by DP. Similar results were obtained with DNSA, but the fluorescence intensity decrease was smaller than that for DP (**Fig.8**). Thus, **Fig.8** indicates that these squaraine derivatives preferably bind to site II non-covalently, and less effectively at site I.

Figure 8. Change in fluorescence intensity with varying concentrations of DP and DNSA to *SQ-215* ($2 \mu\text{M}$)-BSA ($50 \mu\text{M}$) conjugate.

Dyes with $-\text{COOH}$ in *N*-alkyl substitution (**SQ-212** and **SQ-215**) showed more pronounced fluorescence intensity than **SQ-27** with $-\text{COOH}$ directly functionalized to the main ring, which could be attributed to the fact that $-\text{COOH}$ substituted in the alkyl chain has more freedom of rotation compared to $-\text{COOH}$ being substituted on the aromatic main ring. Having greater freedom

of rotation gives -COOH more ability to access the active sites of BSA, thereby increasing the interactions with BSA, which in turn leads to a more effective breaking of the dye-aggregates resulting in an enhanced fluorescence signal.

Figure 9. The plot of $(F_{\infty}-F_0)/(F_x-F_0)$ vs. $[BSA]^{-1}$ of the dyes ($2 \mu M$).

To further compare the ability of the dye's binding and their relative association with BSA quantitatively, the apparent binding constant (K_a) was calculated, as shown in **Fig.9**. The slope of the plot gave the corresponding value of the binding constant (K_a), summarized in **Table 3**. It can be seen from this table that the binding constants of the dyes in this study show an order higher in magnitude compared to typical squaraine dyes⁵⁵. **SQ-215** showed the highest K_a amongst the dyes in this study. Analysis of Job's plot showed that BSA interacts with all the dyes in a 2:1 ratio. The Job's plot for all the dyes is given in the supplementary section.

Table 3. Binding constants for the dyes with their interaction with BSA.

Dye	Binding constant (Ka)
SQ-27	$3.30 \pm 0.03 \times 10^7/\text{mol}$
SQ-212	$2.11 \pm 0.06 \times 10^7/\text{mol}$
SQ-215	$3.61 \pm 0.11 \times 10^7/\text{mol}$

3.3. Interaction of dyes with biological compounds

Compounds **SQ-212** and **SQ-215** were selected as the most promising candidates for further *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* bio-imaging applications. Initially, the Squaraine dyes were incubated with various biological compounds, including 1% BSA, 50% ascites fluid (serving as the medium for growth of NK/Ly tumor cells in mice abdomen), and 10^7 NK/Ly cells. This incubation was carried out in either PBS or water, with the inclusion of a protease inhibitor cocktail to prevent compound degradation and aggregate formation when interacting with cells or ascites. For **SQ-212**, a time-dependent increase in fluorescence intensity was observed, reaching a plateau after approximately 30 minutes. Notably, the highest fluorescence signal was observed when interacting with a 1% BSA solution. Importantly, protease inhibitors had no discernible effect on the compound's fluorescence, as indicated by the signal in the presence of these inhibitors (dotted lines in **Fig. 10**). In the absence of proteins in the mixture (PBS alone or water), the fluorescence of **SQ-212** remained at minimal detectable levels. In contrast, **SQ-215** exhibited a rapid increase in fluorescence upon interaction with the components, reaching 10000 MFI within ten minutes which is 10-fold than **SQ-212**. As with **SQ-212**, BSA produced the strongest signal, while solutions lacking proteins showed no detectable fluorescence. Notably, the fluorescence of **SQ-215** was

nearly five times brighter than that of SQ-212 under the same conditions, owing to higher quantum yield and molar extinction coefficient of SQ-215.

Figure 10. Fluorescence of SQ-212 and SQ-215 upon interaction with biopolymers. Dotted lines indicate the same substance as solid once plus addition of protease inhibitor cocktail.

3.4. In-vitro studies of SQ-212 and SQ-215

To assess the ability of the indicated compounds to penetrate cell membranes, vital microscopy of NK/Ly cells was performed. These cells, characterized by their larger diameter, serve as an

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3 excellent model for studying the intracellular localization of compounds ⁶³. At a concentration of
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5 50 nM, **SQ-212** did not penetrate the cell membrane but got accumulated on the plasma membrane,
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7 as shown in **Fig.11**. This accumulation resulted in a high background signal in the medium
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9 surrounding the cells. In contrast, **SQ-215** rapidly penetrated the cells, exhibiting localization
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11 within the cytoplasm. Although no specific organelle accumulation was observed, some dye
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13 remained in the plasma membrane. As the dye was consumed from the medium, no background
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15 signal was detected (**Fig.11**). Thus, having two similar dyes, one cell-permeant and the other cell-
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17 non-permeant, provides a wide range of options for various visualization applications.
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3 **Figure 11.** *Incubation of mammalian cells with SQ-212 and SQ-215 dyes demonstrated different*
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6 *cell permeability.*

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8 **Differential cell permeability** can be explained by the change in lipophilicity of SQ-212 and SQ-
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10 **215** brought out by the change in *N*-alkyl substitution. The cell membrane plays a critical role in
11 maintaining cellular integrity and regulating the passage of molecules in and out of the cell. It
12 consists of a phospholipid bilayer with embedded proteins that serve various functions. The
13 lipophilicity, or hydrophobicity, of a molecule, is a key determinant of its cell permeability.
14 Lipophilic molecules, characterized by their ability to dissolve in the lipid-rich environment of the
15 cell membrane, can readily traverse the membrane via passive diffusion. However, the degree of
16 lipophilicity must be finely balanced, as excessively lipophilic molecules may become trapped
17 within the lipid bilayer, hindering their passage^{64–66}. The partition coefficient (*p*) in terms of Log
18 *P* value is a quantitative measure of a molecule's lipophilicity, calculated by comparing the
19 distribution of a molecule between a hydrophobic (octanol) and a hydrophilic (water) phase. The
20 Log *P* value represents the logarithm of the ratio of the concentration of the molecule in the organic
21 phase to its concentration in the aqueous phase. The Log *P* value directly influences the cell
22 permeability of molecules. As a general rule, molecules with higher Log *P* values (indicating
23 greater lipophilicity) tend to exhibit increased cell permeability. This is because highly lipophilic
24 compounds can efficiently traverse the lipid bilayer of the cell membrane through passive diffusion
25^{67–69}. However, excessively high Log *P* values may lead to the trapping of the molecule within the
26 bilayer/membrane itself. The log *P* values of SQ-212 and SQ-215 were calculated computationally
27 using the SwissADME tools⁷⁰ and were found to be 10.88 and 8.15, respectively. The high Log *P*
28 value for SQ-212 is attributed to the long *N*-alkyl substitution (dodecyl). **SQ-212, characterized**
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54 **by a very high Log *P* value of 10.88, accumulates within the plasma membrane, unable to penetrate**
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3 into the cell. In contrast, **SQ-215**, exhibiting a comparatively lower Log P value of 8.15 in
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5 comparison to **SQ-212**, permeates the plasma membrane, leading to dye localization in the
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7 cytoplasm as depicted in **Fig. 11**.
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10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 3.5. *In-vivo studies of SQ-212 and SQ-215*

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19 Transitioning from the preceding *in-vitro* studies, the investigation was further extended to *in-vivo*
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21 imaging, allowing for an examination of the compound's behavior within living organisms.
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23 Intraperitoneal injection of a 10 μ M of the dye in H₂O containing 1% DMSO per mouse facilitated
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25 precise visualization of signal distribution within the cell body. Imaging was done using the same
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27 setup at indicated time points. Fluorescence was detected at 720 nm and overlaid with a bright
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29 field image of the animal. **SQ-212** displayed a more uniform distribution, likely attributed to its
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31 lower cell permeability and distribution through the vascular system, while **SQ-215** exhibited a
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33 higher concentration near the injection site, as depicted in **Fig 12**. Importantly, neither toxic effects
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35 were observed nor any behavioral changes were detected in mice up to 7 days following the
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37 compounds' injection. **Fig. 12** illustrates the intense fluorescence exhibited by the dyes in tissues,
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39 affirming the absence of quenching, degradation by the phagocytic system, or binding with blood
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41 components. This accentuates the suitability of **SQ-212** and **SQ-215** as promising candidates for
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43 imaging applications.
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Figure 12. Distribution of *SQ-212* and *SQ-215* in the body of laboratory mice.

Both dyes were excreted through two pathways—urine and stool—following conjugation in the liver, subsequent transfer to bile, and eventual release into the intestine. Validation of this process was conducted through the imaging of both stool and wet bedding within the cage. Notably, the elimination process was more rapid for *SQ-215*, with discernible accumulation in the liver apparent at approximately 120 minutes (**Fig. 12**). Conversely, the removal rate for *SQ-212* was slower, as evidenced by a persistent signal in the liver, intestine, and urinary bladder even after a 24-hour period (**Fig. 13**).

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3 **Figure 13. Weak fluorescence signal shown by SQ-212 after 24 hours indicating slower**
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8 **4. Conclusions**

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10 Three new unsymmetrical squaraine dyes with -COOH functionalization (**SQ-27**, **SQ-212**, and
11 **SQ-215**) and one without -COOH functionalization (**SQ-218**) have been successfully synthesized
12 and characterized. Photophysical characterization followed by dye-BSA interaction studies were
13 conducted to study these dye's applicability as fluorescent probes for sensing and non-covalent
14 labeling of proteins. All of the dyes showed complete fluorescence quenching in PB owing to dye
15 aggregate formation. Interaction of the carboxy functionalized dyes (**SQ-27**, **SQ-212** and **SQ-215**)
16 with BSA indicated the formation of a dye-BSA conjugate, preventing dye aggregation and
17 eventually leading to the enhanced fluorescence signal. **SQ-218**, lacking the -COOH group,
18 showed no fluorescence signal after the addition of BSA, thereby affirming the importance of the
19 -COOH group for the non-covalent dye-BSA interactions. Dyes with the -COOH group substituted
20 in the *N*-alkyl chain (**SQ-212** and **SQ-215**) showed higher fluorescence intensity than **SQ-27**,
21 which has a direct ring -COOH functionalization. All dyes showed very high binding affinities
22 towards BSA in the order of 10^7 /mol. *In-vitro* investigation revealed distinct and differential
23 behavior by SQ-dyes (**SQ-212** and **SQ-215**), where **SQ-212** exhibited no cell penetration, leading
24 to an accumulation on the plasma membrane, whereas **SQ-215** showcased rapid cell penetration
25 and subsequent cytoplasmic localization. Additionally, insights into the distribution of these
26 compounds within living organisms were revealed through *in-vivo* imaging. Both the dyes showed
27 absence of quenching, no degradation by the phagocytic system, or binding with blood components
28 leading to a stable and strong fluorescence signal. **SQ-212** displayed a more uniform distribution,
29 attributed to its lower cell permeability, while **SQ-215** concentrated more near the injection site.
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3 A noteworthy outcome of this study was the absence of any toxic effects or behavioral changes in
4 mice up to 7 days following the compound injections. This non-toxic profile suggests the potential
5 for further development of these dyes for biomedical and imaging applications, while the
6 combination of cell-permeant **SQ-215** and cell-non-permeant **SQ-212** dyes presents a versatile
7 tool for a multitude of visualization applications. The dyes can further be coupled with specific
8 probes for selective tissue imaging, sensing the environment around specific tissues, as well as
9 biomarker detection.
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19 **Author Statement**

- 22 • **Supporting Information-** Detailed synthetic procedures for dye synthesis; NMR and
23 Mass spectroscopy data of the dyes; Jobs plot for dye-BSA interactions.
24
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- 33 • **Author's contributions-** **S.K.M.** and **G.Bss.** contributed by Investigation, Resources, Data
34 curation, and Writing – original draft preparation. **V.U.**, **E.B.**, and **T.K.** contributed by
35 resources and Writing – original draft preparation. **R.B.**, and **S.S.P.** contributed by
36 Conceptualization, validation, Investigation, Resources, Writing – review & editing,
37 Supervision, and project administration.
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